

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

HISTORY OF CULTURE AND ART OF THE EARLY ISLAMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the history of Islamic culture and art, it provides information about the history of the origin, values and development of culture.

Keywords: Islam, culture, art, history, century, Arab Caliphate, values, traditions, city.

The highest value of Islamic culture is monotheism. Sharia is also important in Islamic culture, traditional customs and beliefs that every Muslim must follow.

The concept of "madaniyat" is called by different words in different languages, including "culture" in English and "cultura" in Russian. The word "culture" in the Uzbek language comes from the Arabic word "madina", that is, city, and expresses the dictionary meaning "characteristic of the city", "relating to the city".

History of culture - studies each culture as a unique and inimitable phenomenon; also compares various cultural processes, explores their interaction, differences in time and space, particular and general aspects of cultural development.

Islamic culture - the position of the Christian community played a role in the social, political and moral culture of Europe, America and many other continents, therefore Islamic culture played a big role in the East. Islam is the third and last religion in the world based on monotheism. This religion also originated in the Middle East.

Islam spread not only in the Arab world, but also in the countries of the Middle East, Iran, Central Asia, India, Indonesia, the Caucasus, the Volga region, the Balkans, and large parts of Africa and played a large role in the history and culture of these peoples.

Another important aspect of Islamic culture is that Islam strongly condemns oppression, oppression is blasphemy: "Allah does not guide the oppressors" (Ali Imran, verse 86).

Islamic culture - During the 7th-8th centuries, the Arab Caliphate controlled vast territories of the Maghreb and the East, including the lands of Central Asia. Arab culture and many of its elements began to gradually penetrate into the territories that were part of the Caliphate. The most important thing is that the ideas of the holy book of Islam, the Holy Quran, began to spread widely among different nations. For this purpose, the Arabic language and Arabic writing were introduced in these lands. Beautiful mosques and madrassas, houses and mausoleums, religious and scientific books, libraries rich in manuscripts and other structures adorned

with ornate decorations, which are considered the beauty of Muslim culture, began to be erected. They were built on the ruins of the former material culture of these peoples.

Ideas and values of the "Quran al-Karim" (from the word "reading") (calls of people to correctness, purity, honesty, kindness, generosity, friendship, brotherhood, harmony, peace and tranquility). etc.), Islamic rules, society and people's lives, and on this basis got rid of the previous polytheism, irreligious beliefs and superstitions. Caliph Uthman ibn Affan, may Allah bless him, collected the texts of the "Holy Quran", which were passed down from mouth to mouth after the death of our Prophet Muhammad, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, and created a single perfect text and left a name in the history of Islamic culture. With the help of Muhammad's secretary Zaid bin Thabit and the testimony of the living companions of the Prophet, may Allah bless him, he compiled the only copy of the Holy Qur'an. He then ordered five copies to be copied from a single copy and used in the cities of Mecca, Medina, Damascus, Kufa and Basra.

At the end of the 8th and beginning of the 9th centuries, science developed in Baghdad, the center of the caliphate, and the works of ancient Greek scientists such as Plato, Aristotle, Socrates, Hippocrates, Galen, and Euclid were translated. There was cooperation between Christian and Islamic scholars. After the death of Caliph Harun al-Rashid (813), his son al-Mamun was appointed caliph. He was a man interested in science and culture, until then he was the ruler of Marw (the ruins of which are located near modern Mari) as the representative of the caliphate in Central Asia and Khorasan. After his father's death, when he moved to Baghdad as caliph (819), he founded a scientific center there and gathered scientists from all Muslim countries, including Mowarunnahr. Scientists from Mowarunnahr, Musa al-Khorezmi from Khorasan, Ahmad al-Farghani, Marwazi, Marwarudi and Jauhari worked at this center, who made a great contribution to the popularization of the culture of Baghdad and Arabic science in the world⁷. This scientific center is known in history as "Beit ul-Hikma" (House of the Wise).

⁷ King, David A. (1983). "The Astronomy of the Mamluks". *Isis* 74 (4): 531–55. doi:10.1086/353360.

The Islamic Golden Age is believed to have ended with the fall of the Abbasid Caliphate following the Mongol invasion and siege of Baghdad in 1258⁸. Some scholars believe that the Islamic era ended in 1050. Some put forward the opinion that this period ended in the 15th-16th centuries. The Golden Age of Islam corresponds to the Islamic Middle Ages, and some sources indicate that the Islamic Middle Ages date from 900–1300 CE.

Scholars who worked during the Islamic Golden Age made significant contributions to the development of world education and culture. In particular, during this period great achievements were made in mathematics, medicine, physics, chemistry and other sciences. During the Golden Age of Islam, Islamic culture absorbed the achievements of scientists of different nationalities and religions who lived in the region from southern Spain to China.

The metaphor of the Golden Age of Islam appeared in the 19th century in Western sources devoted to the history of Islam. The author of the Handbook for Travelers in Syria and Palestine, written in 1868, wrote that the mosques in Damascus were “destroying as quickly as Islam itself.”⁹ There is no generally accepted definition of this term. In particular, in the 19th century, some historians equated the golden age of Islam with the period of the caliphate, that is, six and a half centuries, while others believed that the golden age ended with the death of Umar ibn al-Khattab.

In the early 20th century, the term "Islamic Golden Age" was used to refer to the military achievements of the Roshidun, or Rightly Guided Caliphs. By the second half of the 20th century, the achievements of science and mathematics and cultural development in the 9th-12th centuries of the caliphate began to be considered the golden age of Islam. Some sources indicate that this period lasted from the late 8th century to the early 12th or 13th century. Even today there are different interpretations of this term. Although the belief that the Golden Age ended with the end of the Caliphate is based on historical events, some argue that scientific and cultural progress in the Islamic world actually began to decline much earlier.

According to the history of the Islamic world, at the end of the 8th century, paper production was established in Bukhara and Samarkand. Bukhara paper has gained a reputation for its quality in all cities of Central Asia. Particular attention was paid to the writing and design of books, calligraphy; the works of famous scientists, writers and poets of the past were copied and decorated with special paints and designs.

Islam has improved existing beliefs and rules of pure living.

In general, ethics in Islam is a broad concept that covers all aspects of society and serves to create a morally healthy environment.

Islam places special emphasis on increasing knowledge and promoting learning. The Qur'an also called for understanding the divine wisdom of Muhammad, may Allah bless him and grant him peace. Islam, like other monotheistic religions, aims to save humanity from destruction and lead to a pure life.

Islam created a new culture from the products of thought of the ancient East, Greece, Iran, Turkestan and partly India and China. Defending that science is the highest pinnacle of the cultural scene, he encouraged Muslims to study science. He noted that the learned and the ignorant are not equal. By the way, only when a person acquires knowledge does he join the cultural category.

In the lands inhabited by Turkic peoples, the history of Islam took place in a unique way. After Islam settled in Movarunnahr, it spread to the Khazars and Bulgars in the north. The continuous development of Turkish culture has been influenced by Islamic culture. In particular, the spread of Islam among the Oguzes and Garluks gave great results not only in the history of the Turkic peoples, but also in world history. In 960, two hundred thousand nomads of the Oghuz and Karluk tribes converted to Islam.

Islam and the development of scientific knowledge. The Arabic language played a key role in the spread of Islam and its establishment in Central Asia. "The forces that were extraordinary in history and created the period we call the Renaissance" arose during the same period. The great figures of the Renaissance left a deep mark on the history of Central Asia with their practical activities, discoveries in the field of history, philosophy, logic, and exact sciences.

It is known from history that radical changes took place in the spiritual life of the peoples of the East, where Islam spread widely, various rituals and events with universal human values were formed in public life, some ancient traditions were updated in content, and new places for the development of culture and art appeared. In this regard, in the eastern Muslim world, the cultural life of cities of a new (open) type, in contrast to the polities of the ancient world, is especially noteworthy. In particular, in cities such as Baghdad, Damascus, Bukhara, Samarkand, Urgench, Tashkent, along with the organization of international free trade, favorable conditions have been created for the exchange of scientific and cultural values between scientists and artists. At the same time, these cities were centers of universal literacy. Indeed, with the call of Islam, the source of knowledge - reading books - became popular, and to satisfy this social need, libraries began to operate in large cities. In this regard, the Siwan al-Hikmah library¹⁰ in Bukhara was famous in the East for its wealth of valuable scientific works. Naturally, great scientists who grew up in an environment of universal literacy,

⁸ Islamic Radicalism and Multicultural Politics. Taylor & Francis, 2011 — 9 bet. ISBN 978-1-136-95960-8.

⁹ Porter, Josias Leslie. A Handbook for Travelers in Syria and Palestine, London, 1868 — 49 bet.

¹⁰ Абдуҳалимов Б. Байт ал-Ҳикма. Марказий Осие олимларининг Бағдоддаги илмий фаолияти (IX-XI

асрларда аниқ ва табиий фанлар). – Т.: О‘zbekiston. 2010. – Б 8.; қаранг: Багирова С.Г. Сочинение «Татимма сиван ал-хикма» ал-Байхаки как образец средневекового энциклопедического справочника. – Т.: Фан. 1987. – Б 140.

including our great compatriots - Abu Jafar Muhammad ibn Musa Khorezmi (783-850), Ahmad Farghani (797-865), Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048), Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) immeasurably developed the exact sciences (algebra, astronomy, geometry) and medicine, and the great merits of Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950) in musicology laid the foundation of Eastern musical science. During this period of rapid international exchange of cultural values, common traditions and various genres in the classical music of Movarunnahr, Khorasan, Iran and the Arab peoples began to take hold, as a result, professional musical creativity and performance rose to a new level, and in cities and palaces, names famous in the eastern world of composers, singers and musicians, their activities took the form of a painting. There are many references in written sources to the caliphs who venerate them. In particular, according to al-Isfahani's "Kitabulaghani" (Book of Songs), such famous artists as Ibrahim al-Mausili, Ishaq al-Mausili, Ibn Jami and others showed their unique singing and composing talents at the court of Caliph Harun al-Mausili. Rashid (786-809) admits that they received much applause. The high status of professional musicians in our country can be seen in the example of such artists as Abu Abdullah Jafar Rudaki, Alibek Tanburi, Abulabbas Bakhtiyar, Abu Nasr Mutrib, who worked in Bukhara in the first half of the 10th century¹¹. Each of them made a worthy contribution to the creation of musical monuments of the past, based on the requirements and aesthetics of the time. Here it is necessary to note the outstanding achievements of Abu Nasr Farabi.

The patterns used in pottery art were formed mainly in the 10th-11th centuries under the influence of Islam, which spread to Central Asia (8th century), showing the multifaceted artistic talent of folk craftsmen. Glaze and glazing technology, which emerged and were formed in the process of interaction, gave a very rich result in the culture and art of Uzbekistan.

This is evidenced by the presence in Central Asian glazed ceramics of the 9th-13th centuries. ornaments: geometric (geometric), epigraphic, plant (Islamic), zoomorphic, anthropomorphic and others¹².

In short, this religion in its essence not only created great opportunities for acquiring religious and worldly knowledge, but also encouraged everyone to be active in this regard through the hadith "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave." In general, Islamic culture has influenced literature, art, science, philosophy, ethics, customs and education. Islam has strengthened the interaction of cultural values and traditions of the peoples of the vast region.

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¹¹ Тўраев Ф. Бухоро муғаннийлари. – Т.: Фан. 2008. – Б. 23.

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